

Acid Dissociation Constants in Ethanol Water Mixture : Some Hydroxy Coumarins

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The pK_a values of 3-hydroxycoumarin, 4-hydroxycoumarin and 7-hydroxycoumarin in ethanol+water mixtures in the 25-90% (by volume) ethanol composition range have been determined pH-metrically using a combination of glass and calomel electrode system, at 25, 35 and 45°. The thermodynamic parameters ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° have also been evaluated. Increase in the concentration of water from 25 to 90% by volume, and temperature results in the decrease of pK_a for all three coumarins.

ACID dissociation constants in mixtures of solvents have been determined for a large number of hydroxyl compounds by Parsons and Rochester¹, Bates, Paabo and Robinson² and Jagaria and Haldar³. The present paper reports an investigation aimed at gaining information about the specific effects of the position of the hydroxyl group and the variation of solvent composition and temperature on the pK_a values of three different monohydroxycoumarins in ethanol + water mixture.

Experimental

The coumarins were synthesised by the reported methods, (3-hydroxycoumarin, Heilbron and Hill⁴; 4-hydroxycoumarin, Bose and Shah⁵ and 7-hydroxycoumarin, Bridge and Crocker⁶). All other reagents used were of AnalaR grade.

The samples were crystallised 3-4 times before use. The following stock solutions were prepared :

- 0.01M solution of each coumarin (in ethanol),
- 2.0M solution of sodium perchlorate (in water),
- 0.02M solution of perchloric acid (in water) and
- 0.05M solution of tetramethyl ammonium hydroxide (TMAH) (in 50% v/v ethanol).

The titrations were performed on a Beckman-Expandomatic, SS-2, pH-meter (0-14 range) fitted with a glass electrode and a calomel electrode. Temperature was maintained constant with the help of a U-10 Ultrathermostat. For each coumarin at each composition of ethanol + water mixture two titrations were carried out, the first of acid blank containing water, HClO₄ and NaClO₄ and the second of ligand blank containing water, HClO₄, NaClO₄ and coumarin and each was performed at three different temperatures (25, 35 and 45°). Titrations at different ionic strength showed no significant change in pK_a values. The volumes of various solvents added were in such amounts that the final concentration in the solution was 0.0025M with respect to coumarin, 0.001 M with respect to HClO₄ and 0.1 M with respect to NaClO₄. The

final volume was 20.0 ml in each case. The titration vessel, covered with a card board with four holes, was kept in a thermostat, maintained at constant temperature. Glass and calomel electrodes were introduced through two holes. The third hole was used for a stirrer. The tip of the burette provided with a jet just closed the fourth hole. Titrations were performed for all coumarins in 25-90% (v/v) ethanol + water mixture and at different temperatures against standard 0.05 M TMAH solution. The latter solution was prepared in water for convenience. The ionic strength was kept constant in all the cases ($\mu=0.1$ M NaClO₄). Results of titrations of coumarins in different ethanol + water mixtures and temperatures are summarised in Table 1 after making correction for non-aqueous medium⁷.

TABLE 1— pK_a VALUES FOR THREE HYDROXYCOUMARINS IN ETHANOL WATER MIXTURES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES (IONIC STRENGTH $\mu=0.1$ M NaClO₄)

% (ethanol)	7-HC			8-HC			4-HC		
	25°	35°	45°	25°	35°	45°	25°	35°	45°
25	7.86	7.76	7.66	7.16	7.06	6.96	4.36	4.26	4.21
30	8.05	7.95	7.80	7.35	7.15	7.00	4.65	4.40	4.25
40	8.22	8.12	8.02	7.52	7.32	7.12	4.92	4.62	4.47
50	8.32	8.17	8.07	7.57	7.47	7.20	4.97	4.97	4.67
60	8.39	8.19	8.09	7.59	7.49	7.34	5.04	4.99	4.89
70	8.42	8.22	8.12	7.72	7.57	7.42	5.12	5.12	5.07
80	8.57	8.42	8.32	7.77	7.57	7.47	5.34	5.27	5.02
90	8.78	8.58	8.43	7.88	7.78	7.63	5.48	5.38	5.33

Results and Discussion

At any given pH, the volumes of alkali used in the titration of strong acid (HClO₄) and strong acid plus coumarin have been determined from the titration curves. From the titrations performed, $\bar{n}_H$ values have been determined by the following equation used by Bjerrum, modified by Irving and Rossotti (1954)

$$\bar{n}_H = Y + \frac{(v' - v'')(N_B + E^0)}{(v^0 + v' + v'')T_Z^0} \quad (1)$$

where Y = number of dissociable protons (for monohydroxycoumarins used $Y=1$), v' and v'' are the volumes of base (TMAH) of N_B molarity added to a strong acid solution (acid blank) and to strong acid and coumarin solution respectively at a given pH , v^0 = total volume of solution and E^0 and T_L^0 are the concentrations of strong acid and coumarin respectively. When the concentration of undissociated coumarin is negligible compared to that of dissociated coumarin, pK_a value is given by

$$pK_a = pH + \log \frac{\bar{n}_H}{1 - \bar{n}_H} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

The pK_a values were obtained from the intercepts of the plots of $\log \bar{n}_H / (1 - \bar{n}_H)$ vs pH . The pK_a values for all coumarins in different compositions of ethanol + water mixture are recorded in Table 1.

The variation of pK_a with concentration of ethanol in the solvents mixture suggests that the acid dissociation constants (K_a) decrease with the increase in % ethanol in the mixture. This is in agreement with the expectation that the ionisation of the acid should decrease with the decrease in the dielectric constant of the solvent, as observed with other acids. A least squares fit analysis indicates the following linear relationships between the experimentally determined pK_a values and % ethanol.

3-hydroxycoumarin : $pK_a = 0.0097$ (% ethanol) + 6.8843, Correlation coeff. = 0.9657.

4-hydroxycoumarin : $pK_a = 0.0169$ (% ethanol) + 3.9350, Correlation coeff. = 0.9759.

7-hydroxycoumarin : $pK_a = 0.0103$ (% ethanol) + 7.6020, Correlation coeff. = 0.9545.

The temperature effect on pK_a values reveals that as the temperature increases, pK_a values decrease which is in agreement with the conclusion reached by Pitzer⁸. The thermodynamic parameters ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° have been calculated at 25° and reported in Table 2.

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR THREE HYDROXYCOUMARINS AT 25°

Coumarin	ΔG° KJ/mole	ΔH° KJ/mole	ΔS° J/deg/mole
7-HC	47.49	23.65	-80.0
3-HC	43.21	27.95	-53.2
4-HC	28.37	28.72	+ 1.17

Conclusion : We have made an attempt to ascertain the effect of variation of the concentration of water in water-ethanol mixture on the acid dissociation constants (K_a) of coumarins. The trends of change of pK_a values with change in water concentration in the mixtures have been found to be the same as expected from the relation of acid dissociation constant with the change in dielectric constant of the medium.

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References

- G. H. PARSON and C. H. ROCHESTER, *J. Chem. Soc. Faraday Trans. I*, 1974, 1058.
- R. C. BATES, M. PAABO and R. A. ROBINSON, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, 33, 1833.
- S. R. JAGARIA and B. C. HALDAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 40, 287.
- I. M. HEILBRON and D. HILL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 1705.
- J. L. BOSE, V. R. SHAH and R. C. SHAH, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, 666.
- W. BRIDGE, A. J. CROCKER, T. CUBIN and A. ROBERTSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1538.
- L. G. VAN UITERT and C. C. HASS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 451.
- K. S. PITZER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 2365
- K. B. YATSIMIRSKII and V. P. VASIL'EV, "Instability Constants of Complex Compounds", Pergamon Press, N. Y., 1960.